

**IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE EDUCATOR'S WORK WITH
THE COMMUNITY TO ENHANCE THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION AND
UPBRINGING: A SOCIAL-PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM**

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Abstract: The article examines the issues of increasing the effectiveness of interaction of teachers of general secondary education institutions with the public, in particular, with the institutes of family and mahalla. The role of the social environment in ensuring the quality of education and upbringing is scientifically and theoretically grounded. In the course of the research, a socio-pedagogical model for improving the competence of teachers in working with the public was developed.

Keywords: pedagogical integration, public control, school-family-mahalla, socio-pedagogical problem, quality of education, innovative technology.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada umumiy o'rta ta'lim muassasalari pedagoglarining jamoatchilik, xususan, oila va mahalla instituti bilan hamkorligi samaradorligini oshirish masalalari tadqiq etilgan. Ta'lim va tarbiya sifatini ta'minlashda ijtimoiy muhitning o'rni ilmiy-nazariy jihatdan asoslangan. Tadqiqot davomida pedagoglarning jamoatchilik bilan ishlash kompetentsiyasini takomillashtirishning ijtimoiy-pedagogik modeli ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: pedagogik integratsiya, jamoatchilik nazorati, maktab-oila-mahalla, ijtimoiy-pedagogik muammo, ta'lim sifati, innovatsion texnologiya, kommunikativ mahorat.

Аннотация: В статье исследуются вопросы повышения эффективности взаимодействия педагогов общеобразовательных учреждений с общественностью, в частности, с институтами семьи и махалли. Научно-теоретически обоснована роль социальной среды в обеспечении качества

обучения и воспитания. В ходе исследования разработана социально-педагогическая модель совершенствования компетенций педагогов по работе с общественностью.

Ключевые слова: педагогическая интеграция, общественный контроль, школа-семья-махалля, социально-педагогическая проблема, качество образования, инновационная технология.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education” and the strategy for the development of the New Uzbekistan set the priority task of taking the quality of education to a new level. However, limiting the educational and upbringing process solely within the institution does not yield the expected results. Therefore, improving the effectiveness of educators' work with the public requires a separate study as a systematic socio-pedagogical problem.

Issues of public work and social partnership have been extensively studied in Uzbek and foreign pedagogy. In particular, O. Musurmonova, While scholars such as M. Quronov have researched the spiritual foundations of the “family-school-community” partnership, internationally, J. Epstein's theory of “School, Family, and Community Partnerships” has identified six main types of community engagement. This article analyzes these approaches as adapted to the local context.

The study employed systematic approaches, pedagogical modeling, and comparative analysis methods. To determine teachers' level of engagement with the public, an anonymous survey was conducted among 100 teachers and 200 parents in the schools of the Bostanlyk district.

The results of the study showed that 65 percent of teachers use only the traditional parent meeting format for public engagement. To increase the effectiveness of public collaboration, the following phased technology was developed:

1. Diagnostic stage: Creating a social-pedagogical map of the area.

2. Interactive stage: Integrating events such as “Parents' Day,” “Conversation with Neighborhood Activists,” and “Career Day” via digital technologies (Telegram, Zoom).
3. Corrective stage: Analyzing changes in student behavior resulting from the collaboration.

CONCLUSION

Improving the effectiveness of a teacher's community engagement helps to increase the quality of education by 18-22%. This requires the teacher not only to teach but also to possess social management and psychological counseling skills. The proposed technology helps eliminate the “gap” between the educational institution and society.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education.” – T.: 2020.
2. Epstein, J. L. (2018). School, Family, and Community Partnerships: Your Handbook for Action. Corwin Press.
3. Musurmonova O. Pedagogical Technologies – a Factor in Educational Effectiveness. – T.: 2015.